
THE INFLUENCE OF GLOBALIZATION ON AFRICAN SELF INITIATED CHURCHES: A
HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

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INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that one of the major challenges of the 21st century is globalization. The wave of global economy is affecting every other sphere in the modern dispensation. Globalization has become a modern currency that is currently influencing even the most remotest parts of the globe. This modern phenomenon has the capacity of unifying global economy, politics, technology, culture and even religion. Whether globalization is a good thing or a bad thing rather depends on the individuals. The critics of the trend suggest that it may lead to a homogenization of cultures and everyday life, coupled with lack of respect for the individuals in the society and as well the disruption of national identities.

Its supporters, however, see the movement as an outcome of progress, believing that the proliferation of media technology will lead to a global village, in which a global television audience watches and it is shaped by the same entertainment spectacles, political events and economic development (Ilori, 2005).

The presenter of this paper therefore, attempts to unveil the extent on which the modern trend on globalization in the field of Christian religion has influenced African Self Initiated Churches (ASICs). In order to do justice to the above subject, concepts such as globalization and ASICs needed to be explained with a brief historical antecedent on Nigerian Christianity with greater emphasis on indigenization. Furthermore, detail discussion on globalized Christianity versus ASICs especially their meeting points and parallel points, future prospects and then concluding remark.

The Concept of Globalization

The terminology, "globalization" is best described rather than definition. This is because there is divergence opinions regards what the word stands for. P.S. Heslam, presents three school of thoughts on globalization which include globalists school who argues that the beginning of globalization is as a result of the emerging single global economy, transcending and integrating major economic and regions. Second, Demythologizists opted for world's political-economic systems that are breaking up into regional civilization blocks with their own religions, cultural and ethnic rivalries as the genesis of globalization. Third, restructuralists argue that globalization is the transforming and restructuring the economic and political power of nation states. Therefore, authority in society is becoming increasingly diffused among public and private agencies at local, national, regional and global levels (Heslam, 2006).

Historically, proponents of globalization have argued the beginnings of globalization; the estimate of when it all began varies. Some argued that globalization started at the drawn of civilization when men learnt to trade and exchange goods and ideas. Others opined that it is closely related to the emergence of capitalism and the modern era. Further exponents pitch their tent with post industrial period, "a phenomenon of disorganized and highly mobile capital." (Tiplady, 2003). A synthesis of the above arguments accepts the fact that there has been a sudden increased awareness of global praxis in recent years. Suffice to give explanation of what is not globalization before an attempt shall be made to elucidate the meaning.

Globalization is not simply the same as Westernization as some have argued from different angles, neither is it merely about economics; it is much more than that. It is not a world that is "thrown around" in almost all spheres of life. The discussions are no less in Parliaments, corporate boardrooms and labour gatherings. It is not a situation whereby a section of the globe dominates the other in the name of civilization (Tiplady, 2003).

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That means globalization is giving birth to a multi-dimensional new world, that is, the new world has respect for every voice in the global market. It follows that globalization is not just about economics, but evident in many other areas of human life in the copious unstoppable migrations of humanity around the globe. Therefore, it is not a one-way traffic running from the West to the rest of the world. Globalization explains how ideas and structures that rotate around the world are adopted to suit particular local realities. It influences an environment, yet with a close attention to the local tastes and values (Oyemomi, 2005). In fact, one part of the world has connection with other parts of the world except when a part refuses to make her voice known in the global arena. Global connection manifests itself in many ways like trading arrangements which can shape the financial destiny of any particular nation.

The descriptive definition given by (Tiplady, 2003) cited by (Oyemomi, 2005) will be considered as workable definition on this paper. He defined it as: Globalization refers to increasing global interconnectedness, so that events and developments in one part of the world are affected by, have to take account of, and also influenced, in turn, other parts of the world. It also refers to an increasing sense of a single global whole.

African Self-Initiated Churches (ASICs)

Turner, in his classification regards the above as the New Movement of Ethiopianism. While the latter stressed on independence, the former (ASICs) targets on the Holy Spirit which earned her the name Zionism. The Zionists emphasized on the presence of the Holy Spirit power, protection from dangers and evil powers, prophecy, fasting and consecration of Holy Water through prayers. (Turner, 1967 and Ayegboyin, 2002).

The failure of the church in finding solution to the disastrous influenza epidemic that invaded West Africa in A.D. 1918, for which prayer and fasting were recommended as antidotes through revelation by Joseph B. Shadore and Sophia Odunlami led to the evolution of the above prophetic and praying groups. (Sanneh, 1983, ORITA Dec. 1970, and Omoyajowo, 1982). Consequently, the parting ways between the old and the new became inevitable. Oshitelu, Josiah Olunowo was dismissed from the Anglican Church to form the church of the Lord (Aladura) in February 2nd, 1926, because of his prayers. Others include Eternal sacred Order of the Cherubim and Seraphim societies and Apostolic Churches which emerged independently especially from Western Nigeria (Omoyajowo, 1982).

Moving towards the South-South of Nigeria was a notable figure in the person of Garrick Sokari Braide. He hailed from Kalabari of the Ijaw stuff who claimed to have had a vision from God, commissioning him to be His prophet to his people. His evangelistic zeal, coupled with miraculous acts resulted to the formation of "Christ Army". After his death in A.D. 1918, the above church recorded 43,000 membership in the three sections into which it was divided in the Niger Delta areas. His success was attributed to his perfect mastering of the Ijaw local language in communicating the gospel and healing ability which the mainline churches lacked on the field (Babalola, 1981, Turner, 1967, and Isichei, 1995).

Professor Erivwo, who wrote the forward to Nabofa's book on Evangelist Cornelius Adam Igbudu, commended the courage of the evangelist who did not only Isoko-Urhobonized Christianity, but also Nigerianized it beyond the continent of Africa. He was ranked side by side with Garrick Braide's ministry. He founded a full brown contextual evangelistic campaign team known as Anglican Adam Preaching Society (AAPS) as the official organ for the evangelization within the Anglican Communion in Nigeria. His Isoko-Urhobonized Christian gospel music, coupled with divine instant healing were the motivating force for mass conversion of pagans into Christianity. (Nabofa, 1992 and Erivwo, 1998).

Within the ASICs we have the messianic groups. They were so called because of the charismatic nature of their prophets (leaders), who made their followers to exalt them as messiahs. They do live communal life, camp sick patients in their churches, they live in isolated camps popularly called "Holy Cities", and their prophets are highly honoured and considered as messiahs. Turner, had difficulties in classifying them. (Turner, 1967).

It must be noted that some of these ASICs are either Zionists or Messianic churches. Some other time, it is a

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mixture of the two or completely a different phenomenon that has no Christian colouring but a mere covering up with a Christian name. Whichever case, it must be noted that indigenous church movement in Nigeria has post great challenges to the mission oriented ones. In consonance to the above, Lartey asserts:

In many respects, their practice of divine healing is phenomenological similar to the activities of the traditional priest healers. This renders them culturally and religiously very amenable to the masses of people who find in them a congeniality and familiarity absent from the said, silent, "order" form of worship and liturgy in the Western mission founded churches with their non-interventionist theology (Lartey, 1986).

Information from the internet has attempted to sort out the terminology of ASICs by clarifying the below initials AICs as follow:

One of the problems with any discussion of AICs is what the initials stand for and especially what the "I" stands for. Some people insist that it should be "independent", others that it should be "initiated", or "instituted", or "indigenous". People who are not members of an AIC sometimes think an easy way to solve the problem is to "ask the AICs themselves", but with more than 10000 AICS there is no agreement on what it should be. Some prefer one or another, while most don't particularly care- their denomination has its own name, and they are not really interested in how outsiders want to classify them. (<http://www.geocities.com/missionalia/aic.htm>) accessed 4th June, 2009.

In spite of the problems of categorization, however, there is something to be said for using the various terms for different categories, which do not altogether overlap. They include:

- African Independent Churches are bodies that have originated in Africa, and are not dependent on any religious groups outside Africa for funding, leadership or control.
- African Initiated Churches are those that were started as a result of African initiative in African countries, but may be affiliated to wider bodies that include non-African members.
- African Indigenous Churches are those that have and retain an African ethos, and whose theology has developed a distinctive local flavour.
- African Instituted Churches whose establishment and growth have taken place on African soil.

So the initials AICs could indeed stand for four slightly different and partly overlapping characteristics, and a church group with one or more of those characteristics could be described as an AIC. In Mbon's article entitled: "A New typology for Africans New Religious Movements, he coined a new nomenclature for African indigenous churches as Protectionists. He submits that:

We wish to suggest here a term which is more comprehensive and methodologically more empirical than the ones referred to above. The term we propose is protectionist. It is our strong belief that the theme of protection is one that runs across all new religious movements in Africa south of the Sahara. That is to say, protection is the common, ultimate goal of those movements in spite of any dissimilarities in their methods of attempting to achieve that goal. Protectionism, we

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contend, most appropriately qualifies for what Turner refers to as a typology of tendencies and emphases rather than of individual religious bodies or movements. (Turner, 1979)

From the above, it can be deduced that the members of Africa's new religious movements are in the movements first and foremost because they felt the need to be protected against life's undesirable circumstances and believe with all their hearts that they will find such protection in the new movements. The protection sought may be individual or communal and may include physical protection, spiritual protection, political protection, economic protection, and socio-cultural protection.

We can safely conclude that the search for categorization or technically typologically research on ASICs is an on going process. Therefore, the search is a continuous process and is open to new discovery since this researcher does not know it all. This will lead us to several questions on the relevance of ASICs to the modern globalize world as advocated by 21th century scholars.

Is Mbiti's argument for African Christian theology to be developed from African cultural environment which has come to stay, still relevant to globalized Christianity? (Jenkins, 2006, 148). Second, Kato's concept of contextualization of Christianity in Africa, order wise coined as Biblical theology in an African setting advocated by Adeyemo as cited by Tienou, still relevant in a globalized world? (Tienou, 1982 and Kato, 1985). Third, how relevant are professor Adamo's concept of Afrocentric and Africanness in the biblical text, coupled with decolonized theology and culture possible in the face of globalization; especially as he declared: "That prefabricated churches planted on the continent should transmogrity into African churches of the kind in which Christianity will be incarnated in the African milieu." (Ayandele, 2006, and Ennwosa, 2005). Fourth, did professor Idowu and Agbebi ever dreamt of globalized Christianity when they advocated for indigenous form?

In as much as we do not intend in this paper to give answers to the above questions because of the generation gap difference between advocates for indigenuity and globalization awareness; it is a food for thought. Permit me to say that African Christianity is no longer foreign, but rather they are faced with the influence of globalized competitive religious market. This may have placed some limitations on the indigenouness on African Self Initiative churches. This may be either healthy or other wise. It is on the above perspective we shall examine ASICs versus globalize Christianity.

ASICs versus Globalize Christianity

In Africa, in spite of political, social and economic upheavals, Christian faith has served as a bulwark for cultural defense, cultural identity and cultural transition. African Christian Fellowships have dotted the cities, college campuses and suburbs of the United States. African immigrants have come with religious zeal and expectation not only to improve their lot in the United States but also to be a channel of assistance to their brethren in Africa. (Olagoke August, 2003)

For instance, in the Denver Metro area of the United States alone, there are at least five different African initiated immigrant churches, namely: Hands on Christian church, Ethiopian Baptist Christian church, Agape Christian center, Redeemed Christian church, and Christ Harvest Fellowship. These churches have contributed to the ongoing American religious mosaic brought about by globalization, cultural transition accompanying global migration. Hands on Christian church is a racially and ethnically diverse congregation and it is part of a new religious landscape being created and expressed in different languages, and customs that may sometimes be at variance to what is practiced by Orthodox or main line churches in the united States. (Olagoke August, 2003) In this section therefore, the researcher intents to present ASICs versus globalize Christianity in the light of consolidated Age, the influence of syncretism, the shift of gravity in Christendom, influence of technology, elusion of communal life style, language and what does the future holds for ASICs in the globalize world as a conclusion.

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Consolidated Age

The idea of globalize Christianity presupposed an increased self-awareness and others awareness in which greater inter-dependency, interaction, a possibilities of becoming are realizable, reducing the whole world (Christendom) into a single interactive community (Audi, 2005). This global religious village interaction has changed pervious erroneous ideas formed against ASICs. However, for some, the changing trend of the indigenous churches to the modern way of Christianization is not necessarily because of globalization; but it may be attributed to aging. This is because; the indigenous churches are getting constitutionalized and consolidated. There is the tendency of becoming bureaucratic in nature, thus: making her more acceptable in the religious global market.

Influence of Syncretism

Second, a close observation reveals that globalization is influencing some of the syncretists indigenous church movement because of their Charismatic leadership display. Professor Eriwwo subscribes to the above observation when he declared: "the Igbe worshippers (Water spirit worshippers) have turned their shrines into churches and places of worship" (Eriwwo, 2009). This has become necessary if they would become relevant in the globalized religious competitive market. The implication to true Christian' doctrine and practice is beside the issue but rather seeking for relevance in the globalized world is the most important. On the other hand, the acculturated nature of the ASICs is been eroded as a result of the influence of globalization. Therefore, there is no segment of ASICs that want to be regarded as syncretics, hence the cultural milieu is been tailored to reflect global taste, whereas deeply there is something secret than the ordinary.

The Shift of Gravity in Christendom

Third, globalization has assisted Afro-Americans and Euro-Africans the opportunities to herald African Indigenous brand of Christianity in a foreign culture. In fact, the secret of the shifting of gravity of Christendom from Western world to the South in the 21st century is as a result of the popularization of ASICs that has become a blessing to both Africans and Euro-Americans because, the African brand of Christian tradition has become a competing commodity in the global religious market both at home and abroad (Jenkins, 2002). This makes African Christians in overseas to feel comfortable in a foreign land since African congregations are right at their door steps. Some or few whites who became attracted to African congregations are also part of the latter in their own homeland.

In fact, the dispensation whereby Christianity is regarded as foreign to any continent or race is no longer in vogue. Euro-Americans, especially African renowned evangelists are scattered over the globe for evangelistic work. The slogan scholars in the field of religion do use such as cold or white theologies and black theologies are matter of cultural identity which may not necessarily fit into globalized Christianity. This is because globalization in this paper is used as the integration and interconnectedness of religious concepts into a holistic whole; whereby both white and black theologies may gravitate into a new theology that can be called globalized theology. Beside, this may be aside what various cultural identities hold for the individual society. Therefore, the fact remains that the concept of globalization has helped to popularized ASICs world-wide.

Information Technology

Fourth, lack of information technology and finance, coupled with lack of access to modern sophisticated media houses like cable has post limitations on the part of ASICs in the global scene. Information from the internet agrees with the observation as started below:

Since most members of ASICs were poor especially in the early days, they did not enjoy the same access to communications, media that the foreign missionary bodies did, and so much of their early history and growth is unrecorded or poorly recorded. The much better documented activities of the foreign missionaries were like the tip of an iceberg-visible, but only a fraction of the total mass, which remain hidden from public view.

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The above presupposition of domination of Western world having access into information technology more than the South was attributed to the early history of ASICs. Currently, the story has change. The appropriation of the media and media technologies has become part of the globalizing options available to the ASICs. As professor Ojo has rightly observed;

The media not only act as channels of information, they are increasingly becoming purveyors of ideology, taste, and consciousness. The mass media is bringing about a complex re-ordering of patterns of human interaction across space and time. Indeed global communication has greatly aided the internationalization of charismatic renewal all over the world (Ojo, 2006).

In the same way, this age of ASICs which is characterized by modern approach to prayer, healing, deliverance, miraculous signs and wonders, coupled with proper use of the scriptures with charismatic leadership has also gained attraction in global scene. Some of their founding prophets are either trained in a recognized theological institutions, or the one they established by themselves.

A typical example is T.B. Joshua, the founder of the Synagogue Church of All Nations (The SCOAN). He also founded Emmanuel T.V., a Christian television station broadcasting across Africa, Europe and America with evidences of miraculous activities taking place at the SCOAN. His ministry has attracted such visitors to its Lagos International Headquarters, as Ghana's new President (Professor John Atta Mills), President Omar Bongo of Gabon, the Zulu king (Goodwill Zwelithini Kabhekuzulu and former President Fredrick Chiluba of Zambia (Olaiye, 2009). Apart from the above, there is need for more sponsorship of ASICs programmes in the religious global market. Africans can own stations designated for African Christianity for the purpose of advertising our own brand of Christianity to the rest of the world.

In spite of the above submission, some scholars see globalization through the media as a means of corrupting the African new religious movements. This is because, the modern "youth prefer the western beats to the local artists and hair styles, shoes and clothing keep to the trends on the western fashion scene." (<http://jwsr.ucr.edu/archive/vol5/number1/v5n1a5.php>) Which include choice of Christian preachers to watch out in the television screen. The corruption is perceived through the interaction of the local and foreign Christianity via the cable, which is unavoidable.

The Elusion of Communal Life Style

From historical antecedent ASICs believe in the concept of inclusiveness, which make her to be caring and showing concern for one another's needs. This is one of the secret of the accelerated growth of the above movement. God has blessed ASICs with the spirit of inclusiveness and fellowship. There is a saying in Africa that a person does not eat alone (Healey and Sybertz, 1996). In consonance to the above, an article presented by Tovi Ferister and Ilan Vizel, entitled "globalization, sense of belonging and the African community in Tel Aviv-Jaffa" asserts that:

...practices of belonging in African migrant labour communities of Tel Aviv-Jaffa in the 1990s and early 2000s, focuses on the physical and symbolic locations of the churches they established, together with the migrants' reflections on new practices of belonging adopted by these communities ... New practices are flexible and multi-layered, connected to varies aspects of the migrants' identities.

This type of religious identity in Diaspora may be seen as selfish and exclusive in nature, yet it has shown religious unity even in a foreign land.

In contrast, the Western world is exclusive in nature. The individualistic tendency in the West is very strong to the extent that one may not know what is happening to his next door neighbour. In most cases, interactions are done through electronic gadgets without physical presence. Although, we talk about globalized world, yet in the

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West, the individual human relation is far from each other. In fact, in spite of the globalized world, loneliness and individualistic tendencies are still the characteristics of the Western life style.

The above communal life style of the Africans on "inclusiveness" is seriously under attack by globalized forces. As rightly observed by Muyale-Manenji, in his article "the effects of globalization on culture in Africa in the eyes of an African woman," accessed from the web site 4th June 2009 asserts that

Children no longer sit around the fireplace in the evening to listen to stories that promote the values of respect, integrity, peace, love and unity, even in the rural areas where this sort of environment would fit best. People-men, women and children- are all engrossed and embroiled in the struggle for survival- the struggle to get a bowl of mealie-meal to fill the tummy at least for the day.

Globalization therefore, is changing the communal life style of Africans, the ASICs from inclusiveness to exclusive-individualism.

Language

Sixth, according to Odozor, Language is a carrier of the world, as Gadamer stated long ago. It is bound up inextricably with traditions and cultures, the very bases on which people make sense of all reality. Interfere with a people's language and you create confusion in their world, in their very self-understanding. From all over Igbo land, in markets, at home and from car radios people tuned into and listened to theological material which would otherwise have been inaccessible to them. There is a certain feeling in the air that the faith can indeed speak to people in their own idioms. There is no indication yet that the audiences of either Ahiajoku or Odenigbo are about to abandon the English language soon. To survive in a global culture the way it is now, they need to be able to interact with others in English as well. However, they want to do so not as pseudo English persons but as Africans who know their roots, who can speak their language and who are aware of what contributions they have made and can still make to general human flourishing. (Odozor, 2000).

That notwithstanding, one of the greatest contributions the Euro-American (Anglo-phone speaking countries) have contributed to globalization is a common language. In consonance to the above, the National Geographic dedicated a special issue in August, 1999 on global culture. It was observed that:

There is no better measure of this crisis than the loss of languages. Over 10,000 spoken languages have existed throughout history, and only 6,000 remain. 300 of which are spoken by a million people. English is taught and spoken by millions, replacing original languages, making it the number one language in the world (Bennis, 2005).

When France adopted the policy of assimilation for her former colonies and the English a policy of association for her colonized conquered territories, little did they know that such policies would in the future serve as impetus for globalization. Euro-American continents enjoy the monopoly of English language in a globalized world, whereas the Africans with her diverse multi-lingua culture and languages is not too lucky; especially the ASICs with most of their charismatic leaders unlettered. The latter set back has slow down the level and areas otherwise they would have covered.

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Consequently, these charismatic leaders either use interpreters or restrict themselves to local environment until some of them are schooled before launching into a larger sophisticated society. Alternatively, for some, their congregation may only come to the lime light after the first generation of unlettered charismatic leaders might have past the baton to the next generation that might be more exposed educationally. Good example is the Redeem Christian Church of God that was founded by Rev. Josiah Olufemi Akindayomi under the initial appellation "Ogo Oluwa Society", which metamorphosed into the former name under the current General Overseer- Pastor E.A. Adeboye. (Ayegboyin and Ukah, 2002).

Lastly, the influence of ASICs has helped to revive African culture and image in the global scene. Prior to the evolution of ASICs, the missionaries with their educated African counterparts saw Nigerians and Nigeria as a place without culture, or at best a barbaric, paganistic and uncultured people. These obnoxious beliefs have become things of the past. This is because African historiographers, African Christian theologians, African literary legends, coupled with the current wave of globalization, have spark debate and reassessment of the African culture and society. This was made possible among other reasons the ASICs, whose influence they derived joy in making Christianity meaningful to the Africans through her cultural lenses.

What Does The Future Holds For ASICs in A Globalized World?

In attempt to conclude this scholarly article, the presenter will like to remind us that: ASICs had consolidated in African soil. Although, the latter religious movement had met with great criticism and opposition from both Europeans and African scholars coupled with the use of derogative names and some of them were classified as non-Christian denomination, yet they never gave up their faith and convictions.

Africa's reaction to globalization is ambiguous. ASICs embrace the change that is forcing itself on them sometimes with open arms and sometimes with deep suspicion. This ambiguity stems from a perception that there are questionable gains from inclusion in a global arena as well as the feeling that the carpet is being pulled from under their African feet.

But today, it seems that the ASICs are the satellite for global Christianity because of her penetrating and charismatic force in the global religious market. She has received attention from European and African Christians' scholar world wide. The study of ASICs is a welcome idea in most renowned theological institutions in the globe. There is no doubt that the gravity of competition in the Christian religious market is centered around Africa, especially the ASICs in particular. The latter is an essential instrument in advancing Christianity in the modern globalized world.

Conclusively, ASICs cannot look at globalization with one eye closed because the issues are inter-related. She cannot protest globalization without offering alternative. She has to think how globalization has influenced her positively rather than negatively. After all, Africa is the origin of globalization. From Africa the first human beings migrated to explore new grounds; civilization and Christianity inclusive (Bennis, 2005).

REFERENCES

Audu, M. (2005). "The Challenges and Prospects of Networking in Missions in an age of globalization: An African Prospect." *Ogbomoso Journal of Theology (OJOT)*. No 10.

Akpoigbe, S.A. (2002). "A Critical Evaluation of the Portuguese Missionary Enterprise in West Africa." Seminar Paper presented at post graduate school, NBTS, Ogbomoso.

Ayandele, E.A. (2006). "Aladara Churches: Legitimate Branch of the Church Universal." In S.A. Ishola & Ayegboyin (eds) *Ecclesiastes*. Ibadan: Sceptre Prints Press.

Ayandele, E.A. (1971). *A Visionary of the African Church*. Nairobi: East African Publishing House.

Ayegboyin, D. (2002) "Typology of Christian Traditions in Nigeria: A View Point." Presented at Post graduate

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school, NBTS, Ogbomosho.

Ayegboyin, D & Ukah, F. K. (2002). "Taxonomy of Churches in Nigeria: A Historical Perspective." *Ibadan Journal of Religious Studies (ORITA)*. V.xxiv, No. 1 & 2, June & December

Akeredolu, J.L. (1986). *The Church and Its Denomination in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Daystar Press.

Babalola, E.O. (1981). *Christianity in West Africa: An Historical Analysis*. Ekiti: Bamgboye and Co. Press (Nig) Ltd.

Bennis, A. (2005, June, 16). "Globalization in 21st Century: Focus on African." *The Guardian* P. 15.

Collins, T. (1993). *The Baptist Missions in Nigeria 1850-1993*. Ibadan: University Press.

Ekpo, M.U. (1980). "Modern African religious movements: problems of research and classification." Ph.D. dissertation. Florida: University of Florida.

Enuwosa, J. (2005). "The Prospect of Decolonizing Biblical Studies in Nigeria." *Nigerian Association for Biblical Studies NABIS*. No 4 Ibadan: Alofe Nig. Enterprise.

Eriwwo, U. S. (1998). *The Life and Work of Agori-Iwe: First Bishop of Benin Diocese*. Benin City: Uniben Press.

Eriwwo, S.O. 74yrs, Lecturing, Interview at Delta State University, Abraka. Interviewed on January 15, 2009.

Falk, P. (1997). *The Growth of the Church in Africa*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House.

Fenster, T. (2004). *The Global City and the Holy City*. London: Pearson.

Hastings, A. (1992). *A History of African Christianity 1950-1975*. London: Cambridge University Press.

Haywards, E. V. (1963). *African Independent Church Movement*. London: Edinburgh House Press.

Healey, J. and Sybertz, D. (1996). *Towards an African Narrative Theology*. Nairobi; Kenya: Paulines Publications.

Heslam, P.S. "Globalization." (2006). *New Dictionary of Christian Apologetics*. U.S.A. Inter-Varsity Press

Idowu, E. B. (1965). *Towards an Indigenous Church*. London: Oxford University Press.

Ikime, O. (1969) *Niger Delta Rivalry: Itsekiri-Urhobo Relations and the European Presence 1984-1938*. New York: Humanities Press, Inc.

Ilori, J.A. (2005). "Forward." *Ogbomosho Journal of Theology (OJOT)* No. 10, December.

Isichei, E. (1995). *A History of Christianity in Africa*. Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmann publishing Company.

Jenkins, P. (2002). *The Next Christendom*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Jenkins, P. (2006). *The New Faces of Christianity*. Oxford University Press.

Kato, H. B. (1985). *Biblical Christianity in Africa*. Ghana: Africa Christian Press.

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Lartey, E.F. (1986). "Healing: tradition and Pentecostalism in Africa Today." *International Review of Missions*. V. LXXV, No. 297.

Manus, C. U. (1997). "The Theological Presuppositions of The New Religious Movement in Nigeria." (Unpublished paper presented at The Catholic Theological Association of Nigeria Convention, Enugu, Nigeria).

Makhubu, P. (1988). *Who are the Independent Churches?* Johannesburg: Skotaville.

Nabofa, M.Y. (1992). *Adam the Evangelist*. Ibadan: Daystar Press.

Odozor, P. I. (2000). "Emerging African Alternatives to Globalization." <http://jwsr.ucr.edu/archive/vol5/number1/v5n1a5.php> Retrieved November 4, 2009, 4 P.M.

Ojo, M. A. (1984). "New Trends in Nigerian Christianity." Seminar Paper presented at University of Ife,

Ojo, A. M. (2006). "The NBC and the Pentecostal Resurgence, 1970-2000: Critical Issues for ecclesial dynamics." In S.A. Ishola & D. Ayegboyin (Eds), *Ecclesiastes*. Ibadan: Sceptre Prints Press.

Olagoke, A. E. (August 15, 2003) "Religion and Globalization: African Christians in the United States." Paper presented at annual meeting of the Association for the sociology of Religion, Atlanta, Georgia <http://www.geocities.com/missionalia/aic.htm> Retrieved June 4, 2009, 5.21 P.M.

Olaiye, T. (2009, February 17). "New Genetherapy shows Promise for HIV Cure." *The Guardian*. V.20, No 11, 010.

Onah, A. O. (1993). "The Prospect of Christianity in Nigeria." *African Journal of Biblical Studies* (AJBS). V.VIII, No 1, April.

Oyemomi, E. (2005) "Globalization and Its Implications for indigenization of Christian Worship." *OJOT* No 10, December.

OZIGBO, I. R.A. (1997). "A Century of New Religious Movements In Nigeria, 1888-1990" (Unpublished paper Presented at the Catholic Association of Nigeria Convention, Enugu, Nigeria) [http://www.bethel.edu/lecture/African Christianity/google.com](http://www.bethel.edu/lecture/African%20Christianity/google.com). Retrieved November 29, 2011 11.35 P.M.

Sanneh, L. (1983). *West African Christianity: The Religious Impact*. New York: Orbis Books.

Tienou, T. (1990). *The Theological Task of the Church in Africa*. Achimota, Ghana: Africa Christian Press.

Tiplady, R. (2003). *One World or Many? The Impact of Globalization on Mission*. California: William Carey Library.

Turner, H. W. (1967). *African Independent Church V. II*. Britain: Oxford Claredon Press.

Turner, H.W., 1979. "A Typology for African Religious Movements." *Journal of Religion in Africa*.

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